

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CULTURAL STUDIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES

(UGC approved Multi-disciplinary Peer-Reviewed Journal)

UGC Journal Serial No. 49228 in 2019 list

Currently Indexed in UGC CARE LIST, Serial No. 159 in 2022 list

Vol. - XIX, No. - XXII

Eds.

Amitava Roy, Ronan Paterson,
Bryan Reynolds, Subir Dhar, Papia Mitra

A Special Publication of
Tagore Gandhi Institute /
The Shakespeare Society of Eastern India

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CULTURAL STUDIES AND SOCIAL SCIENCES

(UGC approved Multi-disciplinary Peer-Reviewed Journal)

Indexed in UGC CARE LIST since 2017

Vol. - XIX, No. - XXII

Eds.

Amitava Roy, Ronan Paterson, Bryan Reynolds,
Subir Dhar, Papia Mitra

AVANTGARDE PRESS

TAGORE–GANDHI INSTITUTE / SHAKESPEARE SOCIETY
AVANTGARDE PRESS

Published by

Avantgarde Press, Shakespeare Society of Eastern India.

146, Sarat Bose Road, Subash Nagar

Dum Dum Cantonment, Kolkata - 700065/

6A, Maharaja Nanda Kumar Road, P.O. Sarat Bose Road, Kolkata 700029.

Phone: (033) 2466 2688/98304 05624/9748726895.

E.mail: profroy@gmail.com, tapu_biswas@yahoo.com

Website Address : www.tgi.org.in

Web Link : <http://tgi.org.in/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/Vol-XIX-No-XXII.pdf>

© Tagore–Gandhi Institute of Cultural Studies & Service-Learning, Govt. Registered,
Govt. Approved Educational and Cultural Society, Reg. No. S/49021 of 2003-2004

Corresponding Editor : Prof. Amitava Roy

Issue : June, 2023

[While all attempts have been made to acknowledge the copyright holders of the source materials used by the Editors and the authors, for any inadvertent infringement of copyright laws the authors of the papers published are solely responsible, not the Editors or the Shakespeare Society of Eastern India or the Avantgarde Press]

The authors of the papers are responsible for the opinion expressed, use of data, graphs, field surveys, statistics not the Editors and publishers.

Typing, Page setting & Cover Design: Tapasya Biswas

Front cover: Mandala Art, Sketched by 11 years old child artist Tapasya Biswas

Printed at:

Mahamaya Press & Binding

23, Madan Mitra Lane, Kolkata -700006

Ph. : 9830532858

Email : mpkolkata06@gmail.com

Price: ` 600.00 (Rupees Six Hundred) only

US \$40

UK £25

ISSN NO : 2347-4777 (Peer-reviewed Journal)

Editorial Board

International

Antony Johae, Ph.D (UK) : Former Associate Professor, Kuwait University. Life Member, Shakespeare Society of Eastern India.

Aparajita Nanda, (USA) : Professor of English, Berkeley, University of California L.A.

Bryan Reynolds, Ph.D. (USA) : UCI Chancellor's Professor, Department of Drama Claire Trevor School of the Arts, Univ. of California

Emi Hamana, Ph.D. (Japan) : Professor, Doctoral Program in Literature and Linguistics, University of Tsakuba

Robert Emmet Meagher, Ph.D. (USA) : Professor of Humanities, Hampshire College

S. Ramaswany, Ph.D. (USA) : Silliman Fellow, Yale University

Sheila T. Cavanagh, Ph.D. (USA) : Chair Professor, Masse-Martin/NEH Distinguished Teaching Professor, Emory University, Atlanta

Syed Manzurool Islam, Ph.D. (Bangladesh) : Professor of English, Dhaka University

National

Awadesh K. Singh, Ph.D. : Director Translation Centre, IGNOU

Dattatreya Dutt, D. Litt : Former Professor of Drama, Rabindra Bharati University, Kolkata

Debnarayan Bandyopadhyay, Ph.D. : Former Vice-Chancellor, Bankura University, Bankura, West Bengal

Goutam Ghosal, D. Litt : Former Professor, Department of English,
Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan, West Bengal

Harish Trivedi, Ph.D. : Former Head of the Department of English,
Delhi University

K. C. Baral, Ph.D. : Former Professor of India Studies, Dept. of
Comparative Literature and India Studies, EFL University, Hyderabad.

M Mani Meitei : Former Professor of English, Manipur University,
Manipur

Pona Mahanta, Ph.D. : Former Professor of English, Dibrugarh
University, Assam

Prakash Joshi, Ph.D. : Professor, Dept. of English Allahabd University

Rajan Joseph Barrett, Ph.D.: Professor, Dept. of English, Faculty of
Arts, M.S University of Baroda, Vadodara

R. N. Rai, D. Litt. : Former Professor of English, Banaras Hindu
University, Uttar Pradesh

Sanjukta Dasgupta, Ph.D. : Former Professor of English and Dean,
University of Calcutta

UGC APPROVED JOURNAL 2017

Serial No. 49228

UGC Journal Details

Name of the Journal :	International Journal of Cultural Studies and Social Sciences
ISSN Number :	23474777
e-ISSN Number :	
Source :	UNV
Subject :	Cultural Studies, English Literature
Publisher :	AVANTGARDE PRESS
Country of Publication :	India
Broad Subject Category :	Arts & Humanities; Multidisciplinary

UGC-CARE LIST SINCE 2019

Sr.No.	Journal Title	Publisher	ISSN	E-ISSN	UGC-CARE coverage year	Details
1	Acta Fytotechnica et Zootechnica	Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra	1335-258X	1336-9245	from June - 2019 to July - 2020	Indexed in Scopus
2	Acta Graphica	Faculty of Graphic Arts, University of Zagreb	0353-4707	1848-3828	from June - 2019 to October - 2020	Discontinued from Oct. 2020

UGC APPROVED JOURNAL 2022

165	International Journal of Cultural Studies and Social Sciences	Avantgarde Press, Tagore-Gandhi Institute/Shakespeare Society	2347- 4777	NA	from January - 2020 to Present	View
-----	--	--	---------------	----	-----------------------------------	----------------------

430	Theatre International	Avantgarde Press, Tagore-Gandhi Institute/Shakespeare Society	2278 - 2036	NA	from January - 2020 to Present	View
-----	-----------------------	--	-------------------	----	-----------------------------------	----------------------

Contents

From The Editor's Desk	i
1. Mother Right and Politics in the Indian Epics –Tapu Biswas	1
2. Caste and Cultural Conflicts: Contestation and Negotiation through Dalit Autobiographies –Bijender Singh	14
3. Gender Roles And Institutionalized Violence As Patriarchal Ploys For Socio Cultural Victimization of Women In Anita Desai's <i>Fasting, Feasting</i> –N. Banita Devi	27
4. Afflictions of Contemporary Society: A Study Based on Finest Indian Short Fiction –Shibani Chakraverty Aich	38
5. A Close Reading of Ayad Akhtar's <i>Disgraced</i> : Negotiating Identity between American-ness and the Self –Gennia Nuh	47
6. Understanding the Causes and Consequences of Populist Movements: A Multi-dimensional Approach –Saibal Sankar Chakraborty & Ram Darshan	61
7. Socio Political and Cultural Matrix of Contemporary Indian Society in Vijay Tendulkar's Select Texts –Priyanka Chakdar	74
8. Memory in <i>What the Body Remembers</i> –Thokchom Linthoingambi Chanu	81
9. Anthropocentrism and Harmony of Man with Nature in the Selected Poems of Margaret Atwood –Phurailatpam Nandakumar Sharma	90
10. Cyber crimes in India: A Hurdle in the Way of Tech-Era –Prosenjit Saha	100
11. Fenvalerate induces apoptosis with cell cycle	120

arrest in *Macrobrachium lamarrei lamarrei*

(H. Milne Edwards, 1837)

–Babli Halder

12. Narrating the Spaces of Growing up: Childhood, Space and the Quest for Identity 140
–Paloma Chaterji
 13. Sites of Faith in the Poetry of Philip Larkin and Arun Kolkatkar 150
–Shirshendu Basu
 14. Borderless Romantic Love: A Study of Rajorshi Patranabis’s Poetry Through Four Texts 159
–Jagari Mukherjee
 15. Ruskin Bond’s *Small Towns, Big Stories*: A Joyful Riding of Erik H. Erikson’s “Life Cycle” from Play Age to Old Age 170
–Riya Ghosh
 16. “Then there’s us: disconnecting, replanting.”: Scrutinizing Ecoprecarity in the Select Works of John Kinsella 178
–Sudesna Som
 17. Effect of E-Recruitment on HR Department Effectiveness 185
In India’s Private Sector
Sanjay Kumar Gouda Y.S.S.Patro Sarbesh Mishra
-

From the Editor's Desk:

This volume spans an exhaustive range of literary, social, cultural and scientific issues. It begins by harkening back to our primitive past through ancient epics. Then it moves through contemporary India dealing with casteism, national conflicts, gendered violence. Global literature is also discussed. Two scientific articles link together disparate realms as cyberspace and biology. The reader is sure to find himself enriched in many spheres.

Dr. Tapu Biswas takes up the fascinating topic of Mother-Right as found in *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata*. Epics evolve over time containing in them the pre-history of the nation with traces of ancient customs and social systems. One such practice is that of mother-right. In *Mahabharata* inheritance of the throne flows not through the paternal line but through the younger sons of the female line of queens – thus society then practiced matrilineal system. *Ramayana* too shows the prevalence of this practice through Dasarath's impotence – children of the queens, rather than the king, inherit the kingdom. Even among the gods Indra is frequently deposed but Sachi remains fixed in the position as Queen of Heaven. Dr. Biswas convincingly demonstrates that *Mahabharata* is the older while *Ramayana* shows a power struggle between matriarchal and emerging patriarchal systems.

Birender Singh discusses how Dalit autobiographies show the cultural conflicts between the marginalized Dalit society and dominant society. For example Dalits eat meat which is reviled by others. But poverty is also a factor since such options are cheap and available as upper castes don't want it. They also had to follow dress codes violating which was considered an offence to upper castes. Similarly Dalit rituals and deities are also on the fringes. Widow remarriage and polyandry are also to be found in these castes. The autobiographies document these clashes. Singh suggests that that Dalit culture should be assimilated by varna Hindus to become more popular and global.

N. Banita Devi demonstrates how Anita Desai in her novel *Fasting, Feasting* deals with the issue of female victimization by various patriarchal strategies. In the novel we see the father of the female protagonist forces the mother to continue a dangerous pregnancy just in hopes of getting a son. When she finally delivered one the mother is greatly happy. Thus patriarchy controls women's bodies and brainwashes women to accepting the superiority of males. The protagonist is denied any choice in her life and all her parents can think is getting her married. Her humiliation when the groom runs away with her dowry is not considered important; what matters is that an unmarried daughter is a disgrace. As Banita Devi points out even the title of the novel implies gender discrimination.

Dr. Shibani Chakraverty Aich studies 13 short stories from Volume II of *Best Indian Short Stories* anthologized by Khushwant Singh. These stories depict societal and humanitarian problems in post-independent India. Many stories focus on sexual and other physical violence against women including minors, and question the corrupt legal and social system that allow such brutality. Others focus on the equally corrupt politicians, on riots engineered for political profits, on greed for money dominating everyone. Dr. Chakraverty argues that all stories reflect the moral degeneration of society and proper education is the only panacea.

Gennia Nuh critically analyses the problematic response evoked in the audience by Pulitzer-winner Ayad Akhtar's play *Disgraced*. The play focuses on two inter-racial couples. Set in post-9/11 America, the audience is left to grapple with the superficiality of tolerance, prevalent stereotypes, American-ness and the right to construct one's own identity. The audience is confronted with the discomfort that results on realizing their own hypocrisy. The play forces the audience to question if identity is inherited or performed, and the privilege to one's own identity formation.

Dr. Saibal Sankar Chakraborty and Dr. Ram Darshan take a multipronged approach to analyzing populist movements. Populism is a movement that speaks for the common people but always is centred round a political ideology. Economic inequality, backlash against globalization, distrust in existing institutions, fear of losing cultural identity, all are components of such movements. The rise of such movements are harmful and development of civil society is needed to counter them. Their research paper stress the need to understand the underlying causes of populist movement and foster democratic values.

Priyanka Chakdar studies the reflection of contemporary society in selected texts by Vijay Tendulkar. In most of his plays the power dynamics between gender is shown to be oppressive to women with men crushing them in various ways. In *Kanyadaan* the Dalit husband tortures his Brahmin wife because he could not free himself of the memory of his Brahmins had oppressed his community. So the wife becomes an outlet of his rage. Again *Kamala* is about exploitation of poor women and that legally married wives are considered to be slaves of their husbands. Chakdar brings out Tendulkar's subtle undertext that the outward show of liberalism hides oppression of women.

Thokchom Linthoingambi Chanu analyses the function of memory in *What the Body Remembers*, a novel on the gendered violence during Partition of India. The story centres round what the female character remembers about being a woman, brought up amidst restrictions; memory makes her obey the patriarchal code. Memory also becomes a driving engine for communities to draw courage and remember aggression inflicted on them in the past. Yet memory can become a tool of resistance as women speak out what their bodies had endured. Chanu points out that in the novel memory both constructs and deconstructs identity and remembering the gendered violence of partition and acknowledging it is one way of moving forward to a brighter future.

Phurailatpam Nandakumar Sharma looks at selected poems of Margret Atwood from ecological viewpoint. In her poems nature is beautiful and diverse. But man is always violent since they have an anthropocentric mentality. They try to dominate nature and so kills and destroys. Particularly her 'Snake poems' show how the snakes are killed needlessly and even consumed. Yet ultimately man's attempt to dominate nature is futile. Sharma observes that though Atwood provides no solution to the conflict between man and nature, she provides a platform through her poetry reminding man that he is a part of nature and harmony is the only way to preserve his own dying world.

Dr. Prosenjit Saha takes up the highly contemporary issue of cybercrime. Nowadays civilization is highly technological, particularly Information Technology dependant. Yet we also know that cybercrimes have risen in the past few years defrauding citizens and putting national security at risk. Saha gives us a detailed survey of growth of internet in India, cybercrime profiles, laws regulating the internet and safety measures

recommended to keep one's data and money safe. This is a very informative and useful article.

Dr. Babli Halder ventures into the field of biology. She presents in detail the cultivation of freshwater prawn which is a major source of protein. However the use of insecticide like Fenvalerate is harmful. The paper presents her research on the detrimental effect it has on DNA of the prawns. It is a thoroughly scientific paper and offers some fresh material, like the prawns!

Paloma Chaterji discusses the quest for identity in Easterine Kire's novels, *Bitter Wormwood* and *A Terrible Matriarchy*. The first book details the trials and conflicts of Nagas as many of them try to get a separate homeland independent from India but fail to do so. Yet the identity of Nagas as Indian citizens continue to be questioned by mainstream Indians. The second book speaks about gendered discrimination in Naga society. Men always are given a space of their own while women have to continuously struggle to get their own space and transform it into a home. Their work is assigned no value. Chaterji analyses how the world of Naga society with all its complexities and conflicts come out through the child protagonists' growth into adulthood.

Dr. Shirshendu Basu compares the religious poems written by Philip Larkin and Arun Kolatkar. Both of them engage with their national religious identity but their perspectives are divergent. In his poems Larkin depicts the decline of faith in England and that the Church has become a shell only without substance. Kolatkar's poem also depicts a ruined temple that no worshippers visit, but he states with full conviction that this is a house of God. He speaks of images of gods in darkness and lumps of stone worshipped as deities that will help you. While Larkin's poems bid farewell to religion Kolatkar's poems speak of a faith that is unshakable.

Jagori Mukherjee's paper is on Rajorshi Patronobi's four volumes of poems. They are love poems but each collection uses different formats. Mukherjee focuses on their differing styles and how the content is present in various cultural contexts.

Riya Ghosh studies Ruskin Bond's short stories in in the *Small Towns, Big Stories* collection in the light of Erik H. Erikson's theory of psychosocial development. These stories cover all stages of development from childhood to old age in individuals. They show how human beings develop over the

years. Gosh points out that Bond's stories are always with joy at life and the developments portrayed fit in with Erikson's theory of Lifecycle.

Sudesna Som scrutinizes the environmental vision of John Kinsella. His poems explore the most pressing issue of our times – how men have exploited the natural environment degrading it to the point of no-return and thereby also destroyed vulnerable people. In particular he shows how white settlers have destroyed both ecology and native human communities. Som brings out how the poet also shows the way to co-existence of human and non-human communities.

IJCSS occasionally publishes unpublished verses or short fiction from various parts of the globe. We close this issue with a short poem "Hope" composed by Pradeep Chatterjee.

Happy Reading

Amitava Roy & Papia Mitra

Effect of E-Recruitment on HR Department Effectiveness in India's Private Sector

Sanjay Kumar Gouda
Dr Y.S.S.Patro
Dr Sarbesh Mishra

Abstract

A contemporary company would be remiss if it didn't have a human resources (HR) department. The HR department is crucial to a company's performance, according to several studies conducted so far. Because it focuses on "bringing people into the organization," recruitment is a crucial activity among the many that an HR department is supposed to carry out. The purpose of this research paper is to examine how the notion of E-Recruitment and other recent technology advancements have influenced the recruitment process and made life easier for HR managers in the current day. People often assume that private enterprises in India have robust human resources departments that make good use of technology to streamline the hiring process, as the private sector is both a major economic driver and one of the fastest-growing industries in the country. So, looking at the private sector in India as an example is the only reasonable way to evaluate this technology's efficacy.

It is a study of causation. Finding the kind and degree of cause-and-effect linkages is the goal of causal research. Similar to descriptive research, causal research is quantitative and follows a predetermined, organized strategy. The data was gathered via surveys administered to human resources professionals in the cities like Bhubaneswar, Cuttack and Raurkela. HR managers, executives, assistant managers, deputy managers, and coordinators. Since the goal is to determine how E-recruitment affects HR departments' efficiency, statistical tests such as descriptive analysis, sample adequacy, normalcy, reliability correlations, and regression tests were used to provide the study's findings. The findings demonstrate that E-recruitment significantly influences the efficacy of the HR Department in India's private sector.

Keywords: India, private sector, human resource management, e-recruitment

Introduction

Large corporations in industrialized nations started to transfer authority from the chief executive to department heads in charge of operations including manufacturing, marketing, procurement, and, most crucially, human resources (HR). This was in response to shifting economic situations in the country. The goal of creating distinct HR divisions, according to Armstrong (2006), was to fill these open roles with qualified candidates. Every day brings new changes to the nature of work due to the extraordinary level of volatility in the corporate world. Human resources' primary responsibility is hiring new employees (Chapman & Webster, 2003). Finding and hiring qualified people is what it is all about. The procedure is a set of actions that a company does in order to find and entice a group of suitable candidates using a variety of practical recruiting strategies (Fisher et. al, 2014). "Skill development" is the driving force behind today's market. More and more, businesses are realizing the importance of hiring the ideal candidates for the ideal positions at the ideal times. But in the past, things were much different; according to Sills, M. (2014), corporate recruiting procedures started to become more civilized in the 1990s. Many companies started using recruiting services to handle all of their hiring needs. Both technical and non-technical employees were hired by these agencies on behalf of these businesses. According to Holm, A. (2010), hiring was based on market demand for labor loads as companies started offering new positions everyday. The daily salary was the favored method of employment for these businesses. Nevertheless, companies started to seek for more technically skilled workers during the 1990s' industrial revolution as a means to boost product quality and production. The year 2014 was the "Sills".

Consulting with personal and professional networks, advertising in the media, conducting executive searches, etc., are all examples of more conventional approaches to hiring. This information is from Holm (2012). Adding, maintaining, or adjusting the workforce is a continuous process that happens regularly whenever policies, technology, location, mergers, acquisitions, or employee resignations alter the business. The hiring process of skilled workers is becoming more important as sectors become more skill demanding and global rivalry continues. However, it is it's harder than ever to find the right people at the right time. Hidayati, H. (2014).⁵ Traditional techniques of hiring are out of date and insufficient to find a sufficient number of competent candidates. The use of complex recruiting tactics or the combination of several recruitment approaches

has become the norm for many firms in their pursuit of these candidates. Referenced in El-Gohary (2012).

Every aspect of a company has seen significant changes as a result of the fast development of technology (Awang et. al, 2013). In order to locate the most qualified applicants, several companies are using contemporary methods of recruiting and selection (Ensher et. al, 2003). Bartram (2000) asserts that in today's society, the term "internet" is essential to any recruiting process. The employment market was exposed to the idea of "job boards" in the early 2000s. That same year, Monster.com debuted as the pioneering recruiting website (Ensher et. al, 2003). E-recruitment is the most recent approach to hiring. When it comes to hiring new staff, the internet is the cutting edge tool. For both companies and job-seekers, it represents a significant technical advancement. According to a 2009 publication by Parry and Wilson. Beginning in the middle of 1980, HR journals began to discuss the idea of electronic recruiting. Improvements in HR effectiveness are a result of future technological developments. The term "e-HRM" first appeared in the industry in the year 2000. In 2014, Sills.

As other emerging nations, India is in a similar predicament. Following technical advancement, big companies in this area also placed an emphasis on E-recruitment (Ahmed, S., Tahir, H., & Warsi, S. W. (2015)). A number of "job boards" are operational in India, including job.com, Mustakbil.com, Rozee.pk, and LinkedIn, among others. Posts on these employment forums help get the word out to those looking for work.

Thus, it is vital to investigate if HR departments in these organizations have become more efficient as a result of e-recruitment programs in a nation that is less developed like India, and whether these programs have had any effect regarding HR supply chain equilibrium. Due to the little number of scholars that have sought to investigate this topic thus far, this work stands out as a singular endeavor. Human resources departments in private enterprises might use the study's findings to their advantage when developing and deploying e-recruitment systems. This research will find out how well these systems work and how far they can go in the future.

Literature Review

The term "human resource management" encompasses all three of these concepts: management, resources, and employees. Management: the process of making the most efficient and effective use of a limited or scarce resource; resource: the state of having a restricted supply of something (Malik, 2013). Resolving problems pertaining to workers is the core competency of human resource management. Recruitment, selection, and training are the three main responsibilities of HRM. in

accordance with work requirements (Chapman & Webster, 2003). In addition, it gauges the candidate's competence in relation to the position's specifications. The HR department is also responsible for evaluating staff performance and determining appropriate pay rates. In 2008, Parry and Tyson published a paper. Work definition and design, staffing, and remuneration and benefits are the three main areas of responsibility for a human resource management (Demirkaya, H et al., 2011). A key part of human resource management is recruitment, which is responsible for creating human capital for businesses. Companies' success is dependent on how well their people do their jobs (Fisher et al., 2014).

Recruitment is the process of seeking out, recruiting, and selecting the most suitable candidates from a pool of qualified individuals. Scholars, D., and Lockyer, C. (2004). Job needs analysis, advertising the position, receiving resumes, interviewing candidates, making a final hiring decision, and orienting the new hire to the company are all parts of the recruiting process. (Furtmueller, 2012). The process of finding, interviewing, and ultimately hiring qualified individuals is known as recruiting (Oliver D.C., 2015). The sources of recruiting may be categorized into two groups: "Internal Source" recruitment, which includes methods such as internal promotions or transfers, employee recommendations, and the dependents of previous employees. Advertisements, schools, placement agencies, job boards, labor contractors, employment exchanges, "External source" recruiting includes, among other things, job portals (M. Badger, et al., 2014). Much like every other aspect of running a company, the recruitment process is essential to the success of any sector (Chauhan, et al., 2013).

In an article, the term "e-recruitment" was first used. during the 1990s. In a 2003 study, Bodea et al. Holm, A. (2014) states that E-recruitment gained popularity in the 20th century. There are two components to electronic recruiting. E stands for "Electronic," and recruiting refers to the steps taken to ensure that qualified candidates are considered for open positions. E-Recruitment is the most recent approach to hiring that significantly utilizes the internet. When looking for, recruiting, evaluating, interviewing, and ultimately employing new employees, many companies use their own websites or job boards. In 2015, Oliver published a legal document. Employers are finding that e-recruitment helps them save both time and money. Employers may preserve application data and utilize the program to easily select candidates (Chapman & Webster, 2003). The advent of e-recruitment has revolutionized the way businesses and their workers do business by raising both parties' incomes and productivity levels. The author is Sharma (2010). Online resources such as newspapers, job boards, social media, and radio stations are at our

fingertips. Skype, Viber, and other online platforms have been used by companies to conduct interviews. In 2013, Marler and Fisher published a paper. With the use of e-recruitment, recruiters are able to find and employ top talent. Electronic recruitment has attracted a larger candidate pool (Parzinger, M. et al., 2013). The two most crucial aspects of electronic recruitment are the reduction of costs and the attraction of a big pool of candidates. E-recruiting is more beneficial to applicants than conventional recruiting methods, according to several academics. Sills (2014).

The use of electronic recruitment processes has lessened concerns about candidates' credentials, expertise, and history in the industry (Parry & Tyson, 2008). E-Recruitment methods have alleviated a lot of workload for HR managers and recruitment firms. E. Galanki (2002). As a result of E-recruitment, the cost and stress levels fell. Walker et al. (2009) found that e-recruitment leads to higher levels of work satisfaction. The recruiting cycle may be significantly shortened with the aid of e-recruitment. By Gopalia, A. in 2011. E-recruitment has simplified the process of narrowing down the pool of potential technical candidates a breeze (Wang et al., 2013). Database administration is crucial for employers to maintain employee profiles and the data and information associated with them. The contact details, qualifications, and referrals of applicants will be saved in these databases. The database will check the applicants' credentials, including their schooling, driving record, criminal history, and prior work experience. According to El-Gohary (2012), this will make the hiring process more efficient and consistent. Online recruiting is more convenient for job searchers than the old-fashioned way of finding candidates. (Deci et al., 2011). As a result, updating the electronic system is a matter of urgency. Srinivasa & Ramaabanu (2014). Shah et al. (2013) said that E-recruitment is a relatively new notion in India. Modern technology is a hallmark of progress. "New Technologies Used to Improve Productivity" (Teo, 2012). The product's efficiency and longevity are being enhanced by the technological evaluation instruments. Source: Agenyi (2013).

Organizational success is attributable to both the E-Recruitment procedure and the HR system's meticulous design and implementation. Source: Pin and co., 2001. Research conducted by Subhani, M. et al. (2012) indicates that candidates have been found to include false certifications and experience on their applications. Consequently, seeing candidates in person is the preferred method of recruiting in developing nations.

Similarly, Kerrin and Katley (2003) highlighted that out-of-date job ads pose a significant problem for both employers and candidates using the E-Recruitment system. Job searchers faced challenges because to outdated job postings and poorly

designed websites that did not allow users to easily discover job portals (Khan,N. et al., 2012).Online recruiting has the potential to be successful for companies if they utilize and apply them strategically. Charfeddine, L. and Nasri, W. (2012). You and Ash (2014) state that in order to increase organizational efficiency and personnel performance, it is essential to integrate E-systems properly and put them into practice correctly.

The contribution of the private sector to India's progress is immense. Since a company's workforce (human capital) is its foundation, several private sectors have moved their hiring processes online. In a 2013 study, Khan et al. With the proliferation of internet connection, Indians are able to apply for more than one job post at a time. Kazi, A.K., & Mannan, M.A. (2013) state that Indian companies are just as eager to use E-recruitment as their counterparts in the West are, after the successful trial in India. Thanks to its cheap cost-effectiveness and quick response: more than eighty to ninety percent of large businesses have their own website and use it for recruiting. H. Imam and S.N. Batool (2013). According to Amin Mohamed et al. (2002), most establishments in India's private sector, including banks, telecom firms, multinational corporations, non-governmental organizations, educational groups, and many more, have begun to use online job boards or their own websites for electronic recruiting.

Research Framework

A researcher may build a theoretical framework for a study by carefully examining the relevant literature. Theoretical frameworks form the backbone of research projects, say many scholars. It is a well-planned, detailed, and elaborated web of relationships between the factors known to be important to the issue at hand, as uncovered by methods like interviews, observations, and literature reviews. As a theoretical basis for this investigation, the following model is being developed:

Hypotheses Development

These assertions of suggested hypotheses are based on the conceptual framework that was constructed for this investigation:

H1: *E-recruitment has a major influence on the efficiency of India's private sector HR departments.*

H2: *In India's private sector, e-recruitment has a strong correlation with HR department effectiveness in terms of drawing in a higher quality and more extensive candidate pool.*

H3: *In India's private sector, e-recruitment is strongly correlated with HR department performance when it comes to the efficiency and economy of recruiting process.*

H4: *E-recruiting has a strong correlation with HR department effectiveness in the private sector of India when it comes to shortening the recruiting cycle.*

The objective of this research project is to ascertain the nature and extent of the relationship between interactions; so, it is being referred to as a (Causal Research project). Causal research is defined by Sekran (1990) as studies that aim to "investigate" certain concerns. Causal study undertaken in order to analyze implications of particular modifications on existing norms. Causal research is organized, quantifiable, and based on prior planning. Also including statistics and several statistical tests, this research work is of a "Quantitative" type. Data collected from respondents via a survey questionnaire.

Results and Discussions

Since this research is based on the behavioral sciences, we employed Cronbach's Alpha to make sure the instruments were reliable. The reliability of an instrument is regarded "accepted" when its Cronbach's Alpha score is close to 0.8. Cronbach's Alpha value for the instrument's total number of elements is 0.89. Nearly 0.7 is the value. As a result, the questionnaire used to gather data for this research may be considered credible.

H1: E-recruitment has a major influence on the efficiency of India's private sector HR departments.

One of the most important determinants of HR department effectiveness is e-recruitment. This leads us to accept the theory. At 14.279, the T-value indicates that even though the projected EHRD is quite low, the independent variable (E-

Recruitment) has a lot of power to predict outcomes. According to the beta coefficient of .73 at a P value of .000, an increase of one unit in the independent variable (E-Recruitment) results in an increase of 0.723 units in the dependent variable (EHRD). With an adjusted R² of .621 and a tolerance value close to 1, multicollinearity is not an issue with this data set.

H2: In India's private sector, e-recruitment has a strong correlation with HR department effectiveness in terms of drawing in a higher quality and more extensive candidate pool.

E-Recruitment and have a strong connection, obtaining higher-quality candidates. As a result, we accept the hypothesis. E-Recruitment has a high predictive power of 11.019, indicating that it is a good independent variable for estimating the quality of applications. At a p-value of less than the beta coefficient is .666; 0.000 this means that the independent variable (E-Recruitment) will increase by one unit for every the dependent variable (the discovery of higher quality candidates) increases by 0.666 units. Companies and organizations are able to locate higher-quality individuals via electronic recruitment. The absence of multicollinearity in the data is supported by the adjusted R² value of .401 and a tolerance value close to 1.

H3: In India's private sector, e-recruitment is strongly correlated with HR department performance when it comes to the efficiency and economy of recruiting process.

The link between e-recruitment and cost-effectiveness is substantial. Therefore, we accept the theory. The predicted cost-effectiveness is fairly high, and the independent variable (E-Recruitment) has a strong predictive power (T. value: 13.119). At a p-value of less than .000, where 636 is the beta coefficient; this indicates that the dependent variable, cost effectiveness, experiences an increase of 0.636 units for each unit increase in the independent variable (E-Recruitment). With a tolerance close to 1 and an adjusted R² of .521, multicollinearity is not an issue with the data. Electronic recruiting is an efficient and economical method.

H4: E-recruiting has a strong correlation with HR department effectiveness in the private sector of India when it comes to shortening the recruiting cycle.

There is a strong correlation between reduced recruitment cycles and e-recruitment. As a result, we accept the hypothesis. The calculated Reduced Recruitment Cycle has a good predictive power of the independent variable (E-Recruitment), as shown by the T value of 13.727. The dependent variable (Reduced Recruitment Cycle) increases by 0.785 units for every one unit rise in the independent variable (E-Recruitment), as shown by the beta coefficient of .785 at a p-value of less than .000. The use of electronic recruitment has shortened the hiring process. With an adjusted R² of .569 and a tolerance value close to 1, the data does not exhibit any signs of

multicollinearity.

When it comes to human resources, private enterprises in India that provide services are trying to make a difference. When it comes to HR, they are overjoyed to be adopting cutting-edge digital features. The tendency in Indian enterprises aligns with the findings of Budhwar and Sparrow (1997) and Abel, S. (2011), who both noted that the service industry has mostly relied on the internet as a means of communication. Their preferred method of communicating with both internal and external contacts is via this media. Just as Ngai et al. (2008) noted, service businesses are pouring more money into HR IT solutions. They are building their own databases that can hold massive amounts of data. They may attract top talent from all across the globe by launching this program and accepting applications from anywhere. The "auto-screening" features offered by e-recruitment software are of particular relevance to sectors providing services, as stated by Martins, C. et al. (1914).

The considerable association between E-recruitment and attracting higher quality of candidates ($r = 0.664$) is shown by the results. It is acknowledged that E-recruitment leads to a much higher quality of applications. That lines up with what Galanki (2002) and Katou and Budhwar (2006) found.

Electronic recruiting is also helping a big number of people get jobs ($r = 0.663$). The number of people using the internet and the number of locations where it is available are both growing rapidly. India is home to around 10 billion internet users. Thanks to the expansion of broadband, accessing the web has also become simpler and more affordable. As a result, many candidates turned to online recruiting since it is faster and simpler than traditional methods. Studies by Awan, Ghouri, and Khan (2013) and Carrillat, F. et al. (2014) corroborate this tendency, with the latter proposing that online recruiting is the only means by which a candidate may submit an application at any time, day or night, without time limits. Online recruiting has several advantages, and Indian job candidates are starting to see them.

There is a strong correlation between E-recruitment and cost-effectiveness ($r = 0.613$ for internal recruitment and $r = 0.471$ for external recruiting) in the results. Compared to more conventional methods of hiring, e-recruitment helps cut down on operational and administrative expenses. One study by Chuhan et al. (2013) and another by Carrillat et al. (2014) both came to the same conclusion. With a correlation coefficient of 0.748, e-recruitment significantly shortens the recruitment period. E-Recruitment shortens the hiring process. Everyone agrees that the recruiting cycle may be shorter using E-recruitment. If everything goes according to plan, we can probably finish the hiring process in a day. When compared to the old-fashioned method of hiring, the procedures are much faster. Faliagka et al. (2012) and Feldman & Klaas (2002) both found the same thing.

Electronic recruiting has a strong correlation with consistency in the hiring process, according to the results. There is consensus that E-recruitment will have an effect on recruiting process uniformity. The findings of this hypothesis align with the research conducted by Ventura, M. G. G., and Bringula, R. P. (2013) and Pin, Laorden, and Diez (2001). When it comes to helping people find jobs, e-recruitment is highly related. It is acknowledged that E-recruitment has facilitated job seekers. (Awang, M., Ghouri, a. M., & Khan, N. R. (2013) & Ahmed, S., Tahir, H., & Warsi, S. W. (2015)) have both reported the same result.

Recommendations for HR Departments

The following suggestions may be given to the HR departments of private sector organizations in India based on the findings of this research and the fact that technological adoption is not mediating the relationship between HRSCM and e-recruitment:

The Indian firms must work together in a "coordinated" manner to develop, execute, and use technology solutions. Executives supposedly "impose" technical solutions, such an online recruiting platform, on their staff. This system is seen as a "burden" by the middle level or first level management since they fail to comprehend the advantages of technology. Unwillingly using a system will undoubtedly diminish its efficacy. All technical solutions do not need to be implemented simultaneously. All of the systems should be put into place one by one. Acquainting staff with new systems ought to be the objective. One typical cause of poor technology adoption in Indian enterprises is the misallocation of substantial expenditures towards solutions that prospective users find uncomfortable.

Future Research Areas

The findings of this research have the potential to impact several domains, including: an examination of India's public sector organizations might be one avenue for future study in this field. Also, it is possible to do a thorough research that delves into the prospect of Indian enterprises deploying full HR Management Information Systems. Similarly, it would be interesting to evaluate the effects of e-recruitment on the efficiency of HR departments in different types of businesses, such as those in the public and private sectors, the service and manufacturing sectors, or very big and small companies. There has to be a lot more study on how businesses act when it comes to using new technologies. With a larger sample size, this research may also be repeated.

Bibliography:

1. Abel, S. (2011). The role of social networking sites in recruitment: Results of a quantitative study among German companies. Dissertation: University of Twente, Netherlands.
2. Agenyi, B. (2013). Mobile Banking and Entrepreneurship in Developing Countries: A case study of Nigeria.
3. Ahmad, S. R., Prasad, K. D. V., Bhakuni, S., Hedau, A., Narayan, P. S., & Parameswari, P. (2023). The role and relation of emotional intelligence with work-life balance for working women in job stress. *The Scientific Temper*, 14(01), 233-237.
4. Ahmed, S., Tahir, H., & Warsi, S. W. (2015). E-Recruitment Transforming the Dimensions of Online Job Seeking: A case of India. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 5(1), Pages-96. <https://doi.org/10.5296/ijhrs.v5i1.6161>
5. Amin, M. A., Orife, J. N., & Wibowo, K. (2002). The legality of key word search as a personnel selection tool. *Employee Relations*, 24(5), 516-522.
6. Armstrong, M. (2006). Human Resource Management. In M. Armstrong, A Handbook of Human Resource Management Practice (p. 3). London: Kogan Page Limited.
7. Awang, M., Ghouri, A. M., & Khan, N. R. (2013). Impact of e-recruitment and job-seekers perception on intention to pursue the jobs. *Management and Marketing Criova*, (1), 47-57.
8. Badger, J. M., Kaminsky, S. E., & Behrend, T. S. (2014). Media richness and information acquisition in internet recruitment. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 29(7), 866-883. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JMP-05-2012-0155>
9. Bartram, D., & Hambleton, R. K. (2006). Computer-based testing and the Internet. Issues and advantages. England: John Wiley and Sons.
10. Bodea, C., Bodea, V., & Zsolt, M. (2003). Human Resource Management in the Internet Age: e-Recruitment and e-Selection Methods. *Economy Informatics*, 3(3), 5-7.
11. Budhwar, P., & Sparrow, P. (1997). Evaluating levels of strategic integration and devolvement of human resource management in India”, *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 8, 476-494. <https://doi.org/10.1080/095851997341568>
12. Carrillat, F., d’Astous, A., & Morissette, G. E. (2014). Leveraging social media to enhance recruitment effectiveness: A Facebook experiment. *Internet Research*, 24(4), 474-495. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IntR-07-2013-0142>
13. Carrillat, F., d’Astous, A., & Morissette, G. E. (2014). Leveraging social media to enhance recruitment effectiveness: a Facebook experiment. *Internet Research*, 24(4), 474-495.
14. Chapman, D., & Webster, J. (2003). The Use of Technologies in Recruiting, Screening, and Selection Processes for Candidates”, *International Journal of*

- Selection and Assessment, 11(2/3), 113-120. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2389.00234>
15. Chauhan, R. S., Buckley, M., & Harvey, M. (2013). Facebook and personnel selection: what's the big deal? *Organizational Dynamics*, 42(3), 126-134.
 16. Demirkaya, H., Özcüre, G., & Eryiğit, N. (2011). An application on the impacts of human resource management in technology management of the companies. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 24, 474-486. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2011.09.045>
 17. Dhamija, P. (2012). E-recruitment: a Roadmap towards e-Human Resource Management. *Researchers World – International Refereed Journal of Arts Science & Commerce Research (RW-JASCR)*, 3(3(2)), 33-39.
 18. El-Gohary, H. (2012). Factors affecting E-Marketing adoption and implementation in tourism firms: An empirical investigation of Egyptian small tourism organizations. *Tourism Management*, 33(5), 1256-1269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2011.10.013>
 19. Ensher, E. A., Nielson, T. R., & Grant, V. E. (2003). Tales from the hiring line: effects of the internet and technology on HR processes. *Organizational Dynamics*, 31(3), 224-244. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0090-2616\(02\)00111-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0090-2616(02)00111-0)
 20. Faliagka, E., Tsakalidis, A., & Tzimas, G. (2012). An integrated e-recruitment system for automated personality mining and applicant ranking. *Internet research*, 22(5), 551-568. <https://doi.org/10.1108/10662241211271545>
 21. Feldman, D. C., & Klaas, B. S. (2002). Internet Job Hunting: A Field Study of Applicant Experiences with On-Line Recruiting”, *Human Resource Management*, 41(2), 175-192. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm.10030>
 22. Fisher, R., McPhail, R., You, E., & Ash, M. (2014). Using social media to recruit global supply chain managers. *International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management*, 44(8/9), 635-645. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPDLM-07-2013-0179>
 23. Furtmueller, E. (2012). Using technology for global recruitment: why HR/OB scholars need US knowledge? Dissertation: University of Twente, Netherlands
 24. Galanaki, E. (2002). The Decision to recruit Online: A Descriptive Study, *Career International Development*, 7(4), 243-251. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13620430210431325>
 25. Gopalia, A. (2011). Effectiveness of online recruitment and selection process: a case of Tesco.
 26. Gouda, S. K., Patro, Y. S. S., & Mishra, S. (2024). *A Study of E-recruitment technology adoption in India. Educational Administration: Theory and Practice*, 30(5), 11804-11812.

27. Hedau, A. (2020). Value Investing: Evidence From Listed Construction And Infrastructure Sector Companies In India. *Romanian Economic and Business Review*, 15(4), 104-114.
28. Hedau, A. (2024). Impact of Macroeconomic Variables on the Performance of the Indian stock market. *Journal of Informatics Education and Research*, 4(1).
29. Hedau, A., & Joshi, V. K. (2015). Under Pricing Anomaly – Empirical Evidence from Indian Capital Market. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*.
30. Hedau, A., & Mishra, S. (2023). EQUITY PRICE DETERMINANTS OF INDIA'S NIFTY NEXT 50 INDEX FIRMS'. *Indian Journal of Finance and Banking*, 13(2), 14-22.
31. Holm, A. (2010, May). The effect of e-recruitment on the recruitment process: Evidence from case studies of three Danish MNCs. In *Proceedings of the 3rd European academic workshop on electronic human resource management* (pp. 91-111).
32. Holm, A. (2014). Institutional context and e-recruitment practices of Danish organizations.
33. Holm, A. B. (2012). E-recruitment: Towards an Ubiquitous Recruitment Process and Candidate Relationship Management. *Zeitschrift für Personalforschung - German Journal of Research in Human Resource Management*, 26(3), 241-259.
34. Imam, H., & Batool, S. N. (2013). Organizational Perception Regarding Specific Information about Job and Organization: An Approach to E-Recruitment. *International SAMANM Journal of Business and Social Sciences*, 1(1), 26-33.
35. Katou, A. A., & Budhwar, P. S. (2006). Human Resource Management Systems and Organizational Performance: A Test of a Mediating Model in the Greek Manufacturing. Context”, *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 17(7), 1223-1253. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585190600756525>
36. Kazi, A. K., & Mannan, M. A. (2013). Factors affecting adoption of mobile banking in India: Empirical Evidence. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 2(3), 54.
37. Kerrin, M., & Kettley, K. (2003), E-recruitment: Is it Delivering? Institute of Employment Studies. Report 402.
38. Khan, N. R., Awang, M., & Ghouri, A. M. (2013). Impact of E-Recruitment and Job-Seekers Perception on Intention to Pursue the Jobs. Khan, NR, Awang, M., & Ghouri, AM(2013). Impact of E-Recruitment and Job-Seekers Perception on Intention to Pursue the Jobs. *Management & Marketing*, 11(1), 47-57.
39. Khan, N. R., Taha, S. M., & Ghouri, A. M. (2011). Bridging the gap through e-recruitment: Evidences from private employment sector in Karachi. *Indian Journal of Commerce & Management Studies*, 2(6), 40.

40. Lockyer, C., Scholarios, D. (2004). Selecting hotel staff: why best practice does not always work", *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 16(2), 125-136. <https://doi.org/10.1108/09596110410520016>
41. Malik, Z. (2013). The Role of E-recruitment Towards Attraction of Workforce: A Case of Telecom Sector Organization. *Abasyn University Journal of Social Sciences*, 6(1).
42. Malinowski, J., Keim, T., & Weitzel, T. (2005, December 31). Analyzing the Impact of IS Support on Recruitment Processes: An E-Recruitment Phase Model. *Pacific Asia Conference on Information System (PACIS) 2005 Proceedings*.
43. Marler, J. H., & Fisher, S. L. (2013). An evidence-based review of e-HRM and strategic human resource management. *Human Resource Management Review*, 23(1), 18-36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2012.06.002>
44. Martins, C., Oliveira, T., & Popović, A. (2014). Understanding the Internet banking adoption: A unified theory of acceptance and use of technology and perceived risk application. *International Journal of Information Management*, 34(1), 1-13.
45. Mishra, S., & Mohanty, M. (2009). *Financing and Risk Management Techniques in Green Field Projects Under Public, Private Partnership (PPP) Model: A Case Study Of Rajiv Gandhi International Airport (RGIA) Ltd, Hyderabad. Interscience Management Review*, 22-31.
46. Nasri, W., & Charfeddine, L. (2012). Factors affecting the adoption of Internet banking in Tunisia: An integration theory of acceptance model and theory of planned behavior. *The Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 23(1), 1-14.
47. Ngai, E. W. T., Law, C. C. H., Chan, S. C. H., & Wat, F. K. T. (1971). Importance of the internet to human resource practitioners in Hong Kong, *Personnel Review*, 37(1).
48. Oldham, G. R., & Da Silva, N. (2015). The impact of digital technology on the generation and implementation of creative ideas in the workplace. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 42, 5-11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2013.10.041>
49. Oliver, D. C. (2015, August). Recruitment Sources and Natal Dispersal of Catfishes in the Middle Mississippi and Lower Ohio River Inferred from Otolith Chemistry. In 145th Annual Meeting of the American Fisheries Society. Afs.
50. Parry, E., & Tyson, S. (2008). An analysis of the use and success of online recruitment methods in the UK. (C. S. Management, Éd.) *Human Resource Management*, 18(3), 257-274.
51. Parry, E., & Wilson, H. (2009). Factors Influencing the Adoption of Online Recruitment, *Personnel Review*, 38(6), 655-673. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00483480910992265>

52. Parzinger, M. J., Ward, S. G., & Langford, M. (2013). Web Recruitment: Impact of Aesthetics and Playfulness on User's Initial Affective Reactions as it Relates to Applicant Attraction. In Proceedings of the Conference for Information Systems Applied Research ISSN (Vol. 2167, p. 1508).
53. [Pawan, S. B.](#) (2000). Evaluating levels of strategic integration and devolvement of human resource management in the UK, Personnel Review, 29(2), 141 – 157. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00483480010295952>
54. Pin, R. J., Laorden, M., & Sáenz, D. I. (2001). Internet Recruiting Power: Opportunities and Effectiveness, IESE Research Papers D/439, [online] Available from <http://www.iese.edu/research/pdfs/DI-0439-E.pdf>
55. Ramaabaanu, R., & Saranya, M. (2014). Importance and Problems of E-Recruitment. International Journal of Research, 1(9), 445-450.
56. Shah, G. U. D., Bhatti, M. N., Iftikhar, M., Qureshi, M. I., & Zaman, K. (2013). Implementation of technology acceptance model in e-learning environment in rural and urban areas of India. World Applied Sciences Journal, 27(11), 1495-1507.
57. Sharma, V. (2010). Impact of e-recruitment on Human resource Supply chain Management: An Empirical Investigation of service industry in Indian Context (Doctoral dissertation, Jaypee Institute of Information Technology, Noida).
58. Sills, M. (2014). E-recruitment: A comparison with traditional recruitment and the influences of social media: A qualitative and quantitative review.
59. Subhani, M. I., Joseph, S., Osman, A., & Hasan, S. A. (2012). Contribution of LinkedIn on Recruitment and Selection. South Asian Journal of Management Sciences (SAJMS), Iqra University, 6(2), 23-34.
60. Teo, T. (2012). Examining the intention to use technology among pre-service teachers: an integration of the Technology Acceptance Model and Theory of Planned Behavior. Interactive Learning Environments, 20(1), 3-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494821003714632>
61. Tohidi, H. (2011). Human Resources Management main role in Information Technology project management. Procedia Computer Science, 3, 925-929.
62. Veger, M. (2006). How does Internet recruitment have effect on recruitment performance? Fourth Twente Student Conference on IT, 30.
63. Ventura, M. G. G., & Bringula, R. P. (2013). Effectiveness of Online Job Recruitment System: Evidence from the University of the East. IJCSI International Journal of Computer Science Issues, 10(4), 152-159.
64. Wang, Y., Sun, S., Drake, J. R., & Hall, D. (2013). Job Applicants' Information Privacy-Protective Response: Exploring the Roles of Technology Readiness and Trust.
65. Yoon, K. T. D. (2009). A study of e-recruitment technology adoption in Malaysia. Industrial Management & Data Systems, 109(2), 281-300. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02635570910930145>